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Mini Review

The Relationship between Energy and Climate Warming

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Abstract

This article highlights that the main causes of global warming are related to the production of military weapons. It has also been analyzed geographically and geopolitically that changes in carbon dioxide in the atmosphere under the influence of anthropogenic factors are one of the important factors shaping the "greenhouse effect".

Introduction

In the modern world, the most pressing global problems facing a rapidly growing humanity are energy problems and climate warming. At the same time, they are closely interconnected.

It is known that warming air leads to an increase in its moisture capacity [1]. This enhances circulation processes, increases precipitation, and increases the frequency of typhoons, thunderstorms, forest fires, floods over large areas, etc., which are currently observed almost everywhere on the globe, leading to great destruction and even human casualties, often destroying buildings and even populated areas [2]. This has become more frequent in the EU and the US. Therefore, it was difficult to understand the withdrawal of the United States from the Convention on Climate. It seems that the economy was more important than human life and suffering for the former US 45th President Donald Trump.

The main part

The overwhelming majority of scientists, specialists, and politicians, including almost all leaders of large and small countries, consider the main cause of climate warming to be an increase in the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere as a result of the burning of coal, oil, and gas to provide energy resources for the rapidly growing population of the Earth, including the development of

industry and agriculture. To reduce CO₂ emissions [3] into the atmosphere, it is proposed to transfer the energy supply to the use of solar energy, wind energy, and other renewable sources. Particular attention is paid to the development of nuclear energy.

To solve the problem of climate warming, an international group of experts on climate change (IPCC) was created. Summits are held annually with the participation of international organizations, leaders of many countries, scientists, specialists, government officials, public organizations, etc. The number of participants in them reaches 5,000 or more. The results of the work done and tasks for the future are discussed. At its 60th Session in Istanbul, Turkey (January 2024), IPCC member governments agreed on the set of scientific products to be produced in the Seventh Assessment Report cycle. Some timelines were also agreed upon and are indicated. The Seventh Assessment Report cycle will also deliver a special report and several technical guidance documents [4]. These include:

A methodology report for greenhouse gas inventories on short-lived climate forcings (by 2027);

A special Report on Climate Change and Cities (early 2027);

Technical guidelines on impacts and adaptation, including adaptation indicators, metrics, and methodologies (as part of the WGII report);

A methodology report for greenhouse gas inventories on carbon dioxide removal technologies, including carbon capture, utilization, and storage (by the end of 2027). In adopting the work program, member governments agreed that the report cycle would utilize diverse literature and knowledge sources, including Indigenous Peoples' Knowledge.

However, the results are not encouraging; the increase in CO₂ concentration does not stop. With the growth in production and consumption of coal, oil, and gas, this should not have been expected.

Results

World coal consumption in the last decade, according to the BP Statistical Review of World Energy, January 2023, did not fall below 8.0 billion tons [5] per year (until 2000, it did not exceed 4 billion tons per year), oil consumption was 4.7 billion tons per year (average for 2016–2020), and gas consumption was 4092.9 billion m³/year [6].

Most importantly, the heat flow from the bowels of the Earth is four orders of magnitude lower than the heat received from the Sun [7] and therefore cannot be noticeably reflected on the surface of the Earth, which should not be forgotten.

It should further be noted that studies of modern warming are carried out in isolation from the Holocene warming, including the warming after the Little Ice Age and the close correspondence of the current warming to the positions of perihelion and aphelion, which currently occur in early January and July, respectively. This is confirmed by data from meteorological stations. For example, on the Fedchenko glacier, the air temperature trend has the following values: 0.0076 for average annual temperatures (Table 1), i.e., in the winter months the trend is positive and in the summer months it is negative.

Also, in the Namangan region located in Central Asia, the temperature trend for the period 1927–2017 was 0.0414 for the winter months, 0.0186 for the spring months, 0.0236 for the summer months, 0.0239 for the autumn months, and 0.0264 for the annual average [2]. And here, the trend in winter is more positive. It should be especially noted that global warming has led to a significant rise in the level and

some expansion of the ocean area, which also contributes to climate warming.

Discussion

In the middle of the 20th century, several researchers, for example, D.D. Ivanenko and M.U. Sagitov began to develop the hypothesis of the expansion of the Earth [8]. As you know, the Earth has a layered structure. It necessarily follows from this that, initially, it was in a molten state, and as a result of gravitational differentiation, the core, mantle, and crust of the earth were formed. This means that the primary crust also had to cover the entire Earth. Then, as the Earth expanded, the continental crust was torn into pieces—continents—which began to move apart, and the ocean floors formed between them [9]. This hypothesis, as noted by V.A. Magnitsky, eliminates many of the shortcomings of other hypotheses, does not contradict geophysics data, for example, about expansion during heating, and well explains some features of the Earth's structure, such as the formation of mid-ocean swells with their median rift valley, the appearance of the Red Sea, etc. V.A. Magnitsky also pointed out the shortcomings of the hypothesis of the expansion of the Earth.

1. Since the area of the oceans is 3-4 times larger than the area of the continents, the expansion of the Earth requires a doubling of its radius.
2. How could the expansion be so uneven that the continents were concentrated in one hemisphere?
3. Why did the Earth exist for billions of years without experiencing much expansion, and only 200 million years ago did it experience such a gigantic increase in volume?

Currently, the question of the expansion of the Earth and its causes has been confirmed by geophysics. Regarding the size of the expansion, the area of the continents should include the areas of the shelf and continental slope. The average depth of the lower boundary of the continental slope is 4 km. According to the hypsographic curve, 60% of the earth's surface is above a depth of 4 km, which is 306 • 106 km². The radius of a ball with such an area is just over 4900 km. This means that the radius of the Earth has increased by 1471 km. Even if we assume that this was over 200 million years [10], then the Earth expanded annually by 0.7 cm - 0.8 cm, a completely possible and reasonable figure.

As for the appearance of mid-ocean ridges with rift valleys in the oceans, in contrast to the explanations established in global tectonics, they can be associated with the processes of separation and removal of continents from each other. As a result of their removal, pressure on the edges of the oceanic plates increases, which can lead to their subsidence

Table 1: The air temperature trend on the Fedchenko glacier.

Months					
October	November	December	January	February	March
0.009 °C	0.014 °C	0.011 °C	0.054 °C	0.015 °C	0.034 °C
Months					
April	May	June	July	August	September
0.016 °C	0.034 °C	0.016 °C	-0.013 °C	-0.010 °C	-0.072 °C

Source: Modern glaciation and runoff from glaciers in the Syrdarya basin [4; - 32]

and, accordingly, the isostatic rise of the ocean floor at the site of the split and the formation of a mid-ocean ridge [10]. It could also lead to a rise in sea levels and contribute to warming.

The above allows us to conclude that global warming is intensified by anthropogenic CO₂ emissions due to the high consumption of coal and oil for the production of weapons for almost continuous wars.

Moreover, in these wars, it is not the fighting soldiers who die, but civilians. According to statistics, in the First World War, the number of civilians killed was only 5%; in the Second World War, it reached 48%; and now almost all victims of the war-90%-are civilians, most of them women, old people, and children [7]. It is still unknown who financed and is financing ISIS and others in various countries, who is arming them, and who is financing the terrorists. Who creates armed opposition under the guise of democratization? There is only one answer: they are created under pressure from arms manufacturers and dealers. However, the production of weapons is mainly carried out by government organizations [11-15].

Currently, due to the production of weapons in enormous volumes, metallurgy and industries using its products create about 80% of the world's GDP. They are the main energy resources and, accordingly, the main supplier of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and the main culprit of modern warming and its consequences in the form of flooding and destruction of populated areas, loss of life, etc.

Conclusion

Here one involuntarily recalls the words of the West German politician Herbert Grul, who considered the Industrial Revolution a historical recklessness and wrote: "For this recklessness, people, following the strict laws of nature, must seriously pay. They will have to pay all their debts, of course, not in the moral sense. The only thing that is taken to repay a debt... is death." However, weapons manufacturers in great countries, to reassure the people, emphasize that this is being done to employ the population, and large expenditures on the development of new, more powerful types of weapons contribute to the development of science and technology and the creation of new types of

energy. But this could still end in a major environmental disaster, the beginning of which is already being strongly felt, or in a "New Big Bang"!?

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